

Preprint: Television and the Politics of Income and Wealth Perceptions in Britain.

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Abstract

Traditional models of political behaviour (e.g., the median-voter hypothesis [Meltzer & Richard, 1981]) have posited that individuals vote according to economic self-interest, leading to increased demands for redistribution under conditions of economic inequality. However, empirical evidence supporting this claim is weak. Instead, perceptual research suggests that perceptions of economic inequality are mutable and subject to various biases—some of which may be influenced by media segregation. These perceptions operate not only at the level of conscious reflection but also at pre-conscious levels, often shaped by political ideology.

This paper explores these dynamics using a mixed-methods approach. We draw on novel survey data (N = 3,002) collected in Britain in 2024, examining patterns of TV programming consumption related to income and wealth narratives. In addition, we conduct a historical analysis of the reception of these programming types in print and digital news media from 2005 to 2024, with a focus on format (tabloid vs. broadsheet) and political orientation (left vs. right).

We find that the narratives conveyed about income and wealth—whether explicitly framed in terms of inequality or not—create a contested space for defining what is "fair," and for whom (e.g., "taxpayers" vs. "beneficiaries," "rich" vs. "poor"). These narratives also reflect widespread distrust in the government as a mechanism for interpreting and responding to inequality. Crucially, we observe differentiation in levels of trust regarding whether concern for these groups constitutes a credible source of information. These differences appear to be linked to varying perceptions of income and wealth inequality, as well as to political orientation and party affiliation.

1. Introduction

In this paper, we explore the basis of public comprehension of economic inequality and redistribution in the British context through TV programming types containing narratives on income and wealth. We begin this introduction by examining how both objective and subjective measures of economic inequality have inspired a growing body of literature focused on public perception. We critically engage with this perceptual literature, highlighting that it often remains agnostic to the cultural basis of sense-making. Such research tends to assume that individuals can hold fixed and abstract evaluative positions on economic inequality without accounting for how these evaluations are formed through culture. In contrast, we adopt a socio-cultural approach, arguing that individuals' understandings of economic inequality and redistribution are shaped by their situatedness within a plurality of often conflicting narratives on income and wealth; proposing that these narratives may have salient roles in both informing individuals' sense of identity (e.g., "Who am I in society?"), as well as their moral and political orientations (e.g., "Who should I be, and how should society operate?").

This paper is intended as an exploratory contribution to advance methodological innovation in the study of economic inequality perceptions, through critical engagements with socio-cultural theory. We offer, in this introductory section, the theoretical basis for our construction of procedures for the exploration of politicisation and socialisation processes—a survey instrument measuring self-reported consumption of TV programming types containing cultural narratives relevant to the comprehension of economic inequality; related to political orientations, perceptions of income and wealth inequality, socio-demographic factors, and political party affiliation; as well as a frequency analysis of the TV programming types in the print/digital news media following a 2×2 typology organised by political leaning (left/right) and type (broadsheet/tabloid). We suggest that these approaches offer benefits in ecological validity, particularly in their attention to issues of multiplicity in inequality-related beliefs and contexts, as well as pre-conscious motivations, potentially responsive to the roles of ideological factors in the very comprehension of economic inequality.

1.1. Perceptions of Economic Inequality and Redistributive Preferences.

Traditional models of political behaviour—such as the median voter hypothesis (Meltzer & Richard, 1981)—were largely agnostic to the contents of public opinion, modelling political behaviour as a function of individual economic self-interest, such that they propose a natural and self-reproducing relationship between the objective state of national inequality and public demand for redistribution (Stantcheva, 2024). According to this model, in conditions of economic inequality—where a majority of individuals fall below the median income line and would therefore benefit from redistribution—citizens are expected to consistently vote in their economic self-interest for parties supporting higher levels of redistribution. This dynamic is assumed to persist in democratic welfare states until economic inequality is eliminated as an objective indicator (Cavaillé, 2023; Stantcheva, 2024).

However, the empirical relationship between objective measures of inequality and demands for redistribution has proven inconsistent (Hauser & Norton, 2017). National levels of economic inequality are rarely mirrored by equivalent levels of political mobilisation or redistributive demand. Instead, studies find mixed and often inconclusive relationships across countries (Schmidt-Catran, 2016). For instance, in the United Kingdom—where economic inequality has remained persistently high for over two decades—explicit political mobilisation around redistribution has been comparatively limited (Cavaillé, 2023). By contrast, France, where inequality has largely plateaued since the global financial crisis, has experienced prolonged and large-scale protests such as the *Gilets Jaunes* movement, at least partially framed in terms of redistributive concerns (Cavaillé, 2023).

Divergence between objective economic inequality and demands for redistribution has inspired scholarship seeking to explain the factors underlying the public's (mis)perception of economic inequality, in order to account for the failures of economic self-interest alone in explaining political behaviour (Cavaillé, 2023; Marandola & Xu, 2021). Since the early 2000s, researchers have increasingly focused on subjective perceptions and individual-level evaluations of inequality. One influential approach is the socio-ecological model, which argues that misperceptions of inequality arise from unequal access to reliable informational sources (Gobel & Caravacho, 2024). According to this view, informational deficits are central—people misperceive inequality because they lack access to accurate, current, and comprehensive national-level economic data (Gobel & Caravacho, 2024). This interpretation assumes that, if individuals were properly informed about the objective state of inequality and their potential gains or losses from redistribution, their preferences would align with their economic self-interest. However, because individuals are embedded within localised socioeconomic contexts, their perceptions are shaped more by lived experience than by abstract, national statistics (Gobel & Caravacho, 2024; García-Castro et al., 2022). In highly unequal societies marked by residential and social segregation (Willis et al., 2022), individuals lower in the socioeconomic hierarchy are often surrounded by others of similar status (Gobel & Caravacho, 2024; Hauser & Norton, 2017). As a result, they may overestimate their own relative position and underestimate the scale of inequality—a pattern consistently observed in the United Kingdom (Hauser & Norton, 2017).

Complementary studies on media, which seek to explain sources of bias in public perception, have drawn on the concept of diffusion—the process by which information about inequality is translated to the public via the media. These studies suggest that reductions in educational and explanatory content across television and newspaper reporting may further limit individuals' capacity to accurately assess inequality, thereby reinforcing perceptual biases and compounding the effects of socio-economic segregation (Mack, 2020; McGovern et al., 2023). A manifestation of this, particularly in the UK media's focus on the poor rather than the elite, may encourage individuals to overlook the scale of distribution and to overemphasise poverty as an exceptional or isolated condition (Chauhan & Foster, 2014; Chauhan et al., 2024). However, it is important to note, how far media representations continue to focus disproportionately on the 'poor' over the 'elite' (Vaughan & Kerr, 2025). A result of a media environment that sensationalises the extremes in the UK may, in part, be a public propensity to contrast both, such that—despite highly skewed income distributions—individuals at the lower end frequently perceive themselves to be situated closer to the middle of the spectrum (Knell & Stix, 2020).

1.2. Conceptual issues in perceptions of inequality and redistributive preferences.

Scholarship described so far has proposed that sources of bias arise from the limited availability of accurate perceptual information in one's environment, resulting in public misunderstanding of one's economic self-interest. Yet we argue that a programmatic informational processing approach holds significant conceptual limitations. First, moral reasoning concerning economic inequality in the public sphere extends far beyond perceptions of economic distribution, relating instead to questions of what is considered *fair* for *whom* and in *which* contexts. Second, the formation of such reasoning may operate beyond immediate consciousness and instead relate to contextualised, non-conscious processes that carry political-ideological connotations.

The informational processing approach rests on a narrow assumption: that political mobilisation around inequality is driven solely by economic distributional perceptions. In practice, however, public comprehension of economic inequality encompasses a broader set of cultural and political concerns—both in terms of process and content. For example, public understanding has been found to include considerations of trust in government, beliefs about who contributes to and benefits from redistribution (e.g., taxpayers versus welfare recipients), and normative ideas about what is morally right or fair (Cavaillé, 2023; Stantcheva, 2024), as well as perceptions of inequality type (Pereira et al., 2024). Moreover, in the British context, these ideas are often shaped by discourses of meritocracy and social mobility (Pereira et al., 2024; Cavaillé & Van der Straeten, 2022)—discourses which frequently involve concerns about inequalities in political voice, social status, and class-based recognition (Pereira et al., 2024).

Where, then, might we look to understand where beliefs about economic inequality originate? To date, much research has relied on generalised explanations and abstract normative principles. For example, Cavaillé (2023) argues that mass attitudes toward redistribution are shaped not only by material self-interest but also by beliefs about fairness. From this perspective, support for redistribution arises when individuals believe it will benefit them materially and when it aligns with perceived norms of fairness. These norms include reciprocity and institutional solidarity—principles that encourage cooperative behaviour and discourage free-riding—as well as proportionality, particularly in market-based and pre-distribution domains, where rewards are expected to match individual effort (Cavaillé, 2023).

Yet, a persistent challenge is that while these abstract principles may help identify the types of policies people are likely to support, they often fall short when applied to specific, real-world contexts (Trump, 2020). Although general beliefs about fairness have been confirmed in quantitative studies of British public opinion (Cavaillé, 2023), qualitative research highlights the conditional and contextual nature of public reasoning. When individuals are asked about specific domains—such as housing, education, employment, or healthcare—they often express ambivalence about the actual effects of inequality (Pereira et al., 2024). Some question whether inequality is inherently problematic, while

others frame it as a reflection of individual motivation rather than unequal opportunity (Pereira et al., 2024).

At the same time, the question of ecological validity—how accurately standardised survey instruments reflect people’s real-world reasoning—remains a critical and unresolved issue. Large-scale survey tools such as the European Social Survey (ESS) and the International Social Survey Programme (ISSP) often measure attitudes using abstract prompts about inequality’s magnitude, fairness, and policy solutions (Marandola & Xu, 2021). While such measures capture elaborated reasoning, an emerging body of literature suggests that public perceptions of inequality may operate prior to conscious deliberation. In other words, perceiving inequality may be a pre-reflective process that shapes attitudes before individuals engage in explicit reasoning.

In the American context, for instance, studies have shown that attentional biases are shaped by both political ideology and social dominance orientation (Waldfogel et al., 2021). Individuals vary in their sensitivity to inequality depending on the social group involved (Kim & Zauberman, 2024). Conservatives tend to have a higher threshold for recognising bias against traditionally marginalised groups (e.g., women, immigrants, Black Americans), whereas liberals tend to have a higher threshold for recognising bias against traditionally dominant groups (e.g., men, white people, native-born citizens) (Kim & Zauberman, 2024). Importantly, these ideological differences in perceptual thresholds tend to diminish when the social targets are unknown or ideologically irrelevant—highlighting the context-dependent nature of inequality judgments (Kim & Zauberman, 2024).

What this suggests in practice is that relationships between perceptions of inequality, evaluations of fairness, and support for redistribution may be shaped by preconscious cognitive and ideological frameworks, rooted in the specific contexts in which individuals form their understanding of inequality. This raises important methodological concerns about the extent to which public opinion survey instruments—particularly those that ask respondents to evaluate inequality in abstract or generalised terms—can meaningfully capture these dynamics. In effect, what people perceive as *present* or *salient* in society may already have been filtered through ideological lenses and shaped by subtle contextual cues. These processes are difficult to standardise or translate into population-wide self-reported measures, thus calling for caution when interpreting such data as straightforward reflections of public attitudes.

1.3. What Might Culture Offer to Exploring Public Comprehension of Economic Inequality?

We suggest that both material and digital forms of culture—and especially the repeated consumption of stories within them—play an important role in shaping how people understand economic inequality. These cultural narratives help the public imagine who is affected by inequality, what its consequences are, what is seen as fair, and where and how inequality occurs, often in ways that go beyond conscious awareness (Kim, 2023). Additionally, the fact that different groups consume these narratives unevenly—and that this uneven consumption can influence political beliefs (Kalogeropoulos & Nielsen, 2017)—opens up new possibilities for studying how people become politicised and socialised.

Cultural forms provide resources for both social identification (e.g., "Who am I in this society and who do I want to become?") and political imagination (e.g., "What kind of society should we build?"). For example, in the U.S., research shows that exposure to ‘rags-to-riches’ stories reinforces a belief in the American Dream, encouraging individuals to internalise responsibility for wealth and poverty, thereby dampening support for redistribution (Kim, 2023). Such narratives reproduce beliefs that emphasise individualism and meritocracy through the cultural framing of the American Dream (Larsen, 2016). These effects may be cumulative; through repeated exposure over time, media alignment with audience preferences may reinforce social distinctions and shape the frames through which inequality is expected, understood, and consumed (Guardino, 2019).

While it is important to acknowledge that media often emphasize certain narrative types that shape social identity and values (Condon & Wichowsky, 2020), we should be cautious not to equate ‘culture’ with ‘country’. Doing so risks overlooking the significant variation that exists within nations. Public understandings of economic inequality can be shaped by exposure to multiple, sometimes conflicting, narrative forms—something that is not adequately captured when cultural analysis is reduced to national boundaries. Comparative research on how people perceive economic inequality often relies on cross-national comparisons (Schmidt-Catran, 2016). However, such studies frequently find that differences within countries are greater than those between them—a pattern well documented in values research, which consistently shows higher levels of intra-national variation, even among countries within similar cultural or political clusters (Hanel et al., 2018). Overreliance on cross-national comparisons can also lead to an overemphasis on dominant or ‘meta-’ narratives. In contrast, socio-cultural theory has long recognised that everyday thinking at the individual level tends to be more diverse than the more uniform perspectives often portrayed at the macro-social level (e.g., by the media), while also highlighting the disproportionate influence of dominant media representations on political behaviour (Howarth, Andreouli, & Kessi, 2014).

Moreover, the impact of media narratives depends not only on the content and framing of those narratives but also on the socio-demographic characteristics of audiences—such as age, education, income, and political orientation (Kendall, 2011; Marx & Schumacher, 2016). These factors shape how individuals interpret, challenge, or seek out framings on inequality (Guardino, 2019). Over time, alignment between media content and audience preferences can reinforce social distinctions and create cumulative effects in how inequality is perceived (Guardino, 2019). Moreover, the media functions as agenda-setters—not only shaping what is seen as important, but also defining what is politically conceivable (Guardino, 2019). The format and orientation of media are key: newspapers, for instance, differ markedly in their treatment of inequality depending on whether they are broadsheets or tabloids, and their political leanings (McGovern et al., 2023).

1.4. Cultural Narrative Types Relevant to the Perception of Economic Inequality and Redistribution in the United Kingdom.

What types of cultural narratives might we expect in the British media concerning economic inequality? As with the U.S.—from which most examples have been drawn so far—the British media often focuses on elements of need, questioning the “deservingness” of recipients and distinguishing, within a meritocratic framework, between valorised contributors and stigmatised dependents, as is a common feature of liberalised welfare regimes (Larsen & Dejgaard, 2013). However, it should be noted that the U.S. focus on “welfare queens” (Larsen & Dejgaard, 2013) may represent a uniquely racialised discourse of the undeserving citizen. In contrast, in the UK, recipients are more likely to be represented through derogatory terms and Othered as the “white” poor—e.g., “chav” and “benefit scrounger”—and ultimately as fundamentally “not-me” (Adams & Raisborough, 2011). These stereotypes often portray young, working-class white people as uncultured, aggressive, and reliant on state benefits (Adams & Raisborough, 2011). For example, in an analysis of tweets responding to the first episode of *Benefits Street II*, a controversial television programme following individuals living on social benefits, van der Bom et al. (2018) find that it encourages responses emphasising the poor as moral failures, an underclass, and even non-human—a feature to be despised in society. However, alternative programs, which make direct comparisons between the lives of the rich and the poor (e.g., *Rich House, Poor House*), may offer more critical and sympathetic representations. To our knowledge the effects of these programs remain unconsidered.

In addition, we may find variations in how individuals are portrayed based on their roles within the UK’s mixed public-private system of income generation. Compared to the U.S., the UK media may present a broader range of representations, reflecting the influence of both public and private sectors in shaping beliefs about economic inequality and redistribution. The UK has been characterised as adopting a “Third Way” approach (Gingrich & King, 2018). The British welfare state emerged as a hybrid model, drawing from both American and European traditions, combining state provision with

private involvement. This model sought to balance the flexibility of the American system with European-style social protections and long-term investment in human capital (Gingrich & King, 2018).

As a result, what is valorised in contrast to the "Other" of the social beneficiary may include narratives that present "heroes" from both the public and private sectors. For example, media representations of the National Health Service (NHS), such as the TV programme *24 Hours in A&E*, highlight the heroic work of doctors and nurses, emphasising their dedication, compassion, and motivation in the face of institutional shortcomings (Timmons & Nairn, 2015). Similarly, expressions of collective sentiment—optimism, compassion, hope, connection, and reciprocity—are evident in reality television programmes such as *The Secret Millionaire* (Nunn & Biressi, 2013). These shows underscore the morality and capability of private-sector individuals who support and uplift others, especially in the wake of financial hardship following the global financial crisis (Nunn & Biressi, 2013).

Yet, arguably, a unique feature of the British media landscape is its strong tradition of satire, which often targets the incompetence and self-serving nature of state mechanisms. This satirical focus may contribute to a public perception that systemic change is futile, as reflected in qualitative research on perceptions of inequality (Pereira et al., 2024). A notable example is the enduring cultural influence of television programmes such as *Yes Minister* (1980s), which have shaped public perceptions of the British political system (Granville, 2009). These portrayals have continued to foster distrust in the civil service long after the programmes ceased production (Granville, 2009).

Narratives about economic inequality may also be found in dramas that depict the 'exclusive' lives of both traditional and modern elites—whether real or fictional—often framed through themes of power and inherited class structures. For example, the portrayal of Queen Elizabeth II's treatment of Diana, Princess of Wales, in *The Crown* reflects this focus (Abbiss, 2023). Such portrayals frequently involve elements of nostalgia, presenting history as something that exists both in the past and the present, while emphasizing the personal morality of individuals rather than broader structural issues (Abbiss, 2023). At the same time, this focus on inheritance and elite status can coexist with a cultural narrative that celebrates meritocracy—particularly through highly publicised stories of self-made success (e.g., *Keeping Up with the Kardashians*, *The Real Housewives* series)—thereby downplaying concerns about equality of opportunity within a meritocratic system (Carr et al., 2023; Kendall, 2011).

Yet, while television programming often sensationalises both "looking up" at the elite and "looking down" at the poor—offering narratives about who they are and how they live—there is also a stream of cultural narratives in the UK that emphasises the "everyday" prototypical person. For example, *Antiques Roadshow*, a programme in which individuals discover the hidden value of personal objects of wealth, is now in its 47th series in the UK, having first launched in 1979. Its enduring appeal is reflected in its continued popularity, often filmed at historic locations across the United Kingdom, with an estimated 35,000 people attending *Antiques Roadshow* events throughout 2015 (National Trust, 2016; Cornish, 2024). Similarly, a number of television programmes have emerged that highlight the exceptional skills, determination, and hard work of ordinary people achieving success and upward mobility—for example, *Dragon's Den* (García-Gómez, 2018)

1.5. Interim summary

So far, we have outlined the important role that perceptions of inequality play in explaining why high levels of economic inequality do not necessarily translate into increased political demand for redistribution. Rather than assuming individuals act solely based on economic self-interest, perceptions of inequality are shaped by broader social considerations, including social identity, the context in which inequality is situated, and beliefs about fairness. We have also noted that dominant approaches to studying these perceptions often rely on models of informational processing. These models typically assume that biases arise primarily from limited or segmented access to information—whether due to economic segregation or media distortions. However, we argue that this framework is conceptually limited. The comprehension of economic inequality may operate at levels beyond reflective or rational

evaluation; it may involve preconscious processes shaped by political ideology and cultural framing. Moreover, public understanding of inequality is not necessarily coherent or unified. Rather, it may be fragmented, partial, and shaped by competing interpretations—resulting in ambiguity and uncertainty in how inequality is perceived.

In response to these limitations, we propose that a variety of narratives on income and wealth may play a underexplored role in shaping and exploring the motivated, preconscious processes underlying public perceptions of inequality. The British media landscape, in particular, presents a diverse range of narrative types related to economic inequality. These include narratives that question the “deservingness” of welfare recipients, valorise the extreme wealth of elites, and romanticise inherited privilege through dramatic portrayals of aristocratic life. At the same time, more grounded narratives exist that focus on everyday success stories and the motivations of ordinary individuals—often reflecting the hybrid nature of the UK’s welfare state, which integrates both public and private sector elements. Additionally, some programming fosters a sense of distrust in the civil service and state institutions, casting doubt on their capacity to address issues of redistribution effectively.

2. Methods

2.1. Summary of Methodological and Analytical Approach

Two types of data collection were employed in this study and are described separately below: (1) a survey capturing public consumption of different types of television programming; and (2) a frequency analysis examining the salience of these television programming types in UK digital and print media coverage, with an added qualitative inspection. We followed a five-step procedure in this exploratory mixed-methods study:

1. **Framework Development:** As described in Section 1.4, we conducted a narrative synthesis to identify a range of narratives on income and wealth, resulting in an initial framework of TV programming types—that is, narrative categories through which income and wealth generation are portrayed in British which hold implications for the comprehension of economic inequality. This framework (see Table A.X) informed the development of a survey instrument, which was administered online in the UK in 2024 to a representative sample of adults (N = 3,002). In the first stage of analysis, we assessed respondents’ current and past consumption with relevant television programming types and collected associated socio-demographic data.
2. **Correlation Analysis:** We explored the relationships between patterns of TV programming types and respondents’ perceptions of income and wealth inequality in the UK. Additional analyses were conducted with political affiliation and ideological orientation were conducted. Beyond the effects of individual programmes, we also explored how breadth of consumption type also related to these perceptions and attitudes.
3. **Factor Analysis:** To reduce complexity in the typology of television programming types, we conducted an exploratory factor analysis. This resulted in a three-factor solution that explained approximately 50% of the variance in the data, allowing for the classification of TV programmes into three partially distinct narrative groupings.
4. **Media Frequency and Agenda-Setting Analysis:** We identified the specific programmes contributing to each factor and conducted a frequency analysis of their appearance in UK digital and print news coverage. This enabled us to explore potential agenda-setting effects, focusing on how attention to different programme types varied by political leaning of media outlets (e.g., left vs. right) and media format (e.g., tabloid vs. broadsheet).
5. **Contextual Interpretation:** Finally, we carried out a visual inspection of media coverage trends at points when specific television programme types—corresponding to the three narrative groupings from the factor analysis—were particularly salient in the news.

2.2. Survey

2.2.1. Procedure

The study employed an online survey conducted in 2024 with a sample of adults residing in Great Britain (N = 3,008). Eligibility was restricted to individuals aged 18 years or older. Quotas for age, gender, and geographic region were applied to ensure that the sample broadly reflected national demographic distributions. To ensure data quality, several safeguards were implemented. Participants who completed the survey in less than 25% of the median interview time were excluded from the final dataset. An attention check item was included to assess participant attentiveness. Additionally, a “soft launch” of the survey was conducted prior to full-scale deployment to confirm the correct functioning of skip logic, filter questions, and randomisation procedures.

The study protocol, including the hypotheses and analytic strategy, was pre-registered on AsPredicted.org (<https://aspredicted.org/5ndg-m8xz.pdf>; <https://aspredicted.org/qrw3-v55h.pdf>). The full questionnaire and anonymised dataset will be made available via Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15046313>) following an embargo period. These files will be publicly accessible on December 31, 2026. The embargo—lasting one year from the conclusion of the ERC Consolidator Grant 2019 POLINEQUAL (866340)—was agreed upon with the funder to allow the principal investigator and their research team time to develop scientific publications based on the data.

2.2.2. Sample

Following data quality screening, the final analytic sample consisted of 3,002 respondents. Gender distribution was approximately balanced, with 47.9% identifying as female (n = 1,438) and 51.8% as male (n = 1,556); eight participants (<0.3%) selected “other” or “can’t choose.” The sample covered all major UK regions, with the South East (14.4%), London (13.8%), and the North West (11.7%) being the most represented areas. Age distribution was also broad: 24.8% were aged 50–64, 23.8% were 65 and older, and 22.6% were aged 35–49.

Household size ranged from one to five individuals, with two-person households being most common (35.6%). In terms of employment, 58.3% of respondents reported being in paid work at the time of the survey, while 23.1% were retired. Smaller groups reported being in education (4.2%), unemployed (4.5%), permanently sick or disabled (4.5%), or engaged in caregiving duties (4.6%). Approximately 63% of participants owned their homes. Household income levels were distributed across a range of brackets, with the most common monthly income falling between £2,190 and £2,659 (11.9%).

2.2.3. Measures

2.2.3.1. TV Programming Types

Informed by a narrative synthesis of cultural narratives relevant to the comprehension of economic inequality and redistribution, participants were asked: *"Have you watched any of the following types of TV programs on any device or service, either recently or in the past?"* To assist in selection, examples of representative TV programs were provided for each programming type (see Table 1). A total of 16.8% of the sample (n = 505) either could not choose or reported not having watched any of the listed TV programming types. The percentages reported in Table 1 are based on the 2,497 participants who indicated having watched at least one of the TV types listed.

Table 1: List of TV Programming Types and Examples

TV Program Type	Examples Given	Yes (%)
Real-life Stories of Everyday Individuals Achieving Success	The Apprentice, The 1% Club, Dragon's Den, X-Factor, The Voice	58.2% (n = 1453)
Real-life Stories of Individuals Finding Unexpected Wealth	Cash in the Attic, Antiques Roadshow, The Lottery Winners	42.7% (n = 1067)
Real-life Stories of the Everyday Heroes Workers in the Public Sector	Educating Essex, 24 Hours in A&E	41.5% (n = 1036)
Fictional Dramas About the Elite and Their Families	The Crown, Succession, House of Cards, Elite, Gossip Girl	39.2% (n = 980)
Fictional Dramas About an Ineffective Government and Welfare System	Teachers, The Job Lot, The Thick of It, Getting On, Yes Minister	34.4% (n = 858)
Real-life Stories of the Everyday Heroes in the Private Sector	The Secret Millionaire, Undercover Boss	29.4% (n = 733)
Real-life Stories About the Differences in Income and Wealth Between Families	Rich House, Poor House, How the Other Half Lives, Rich Holiday, Poor Holiday	29.1% (n = 727)
Real-life Stories of Everyday Individuals Living in Poverty and/or on Welfare Payments	Breadline Britain, Skint, Benefits Street, Jeremy Kyle	29.0% (n = 723)
Real-life Stories of the Everyday Lives of Rich Individuals	Keeping Up with the Kardashians, The Real Housewives	17.7% (n = 443)

To develop a variable representing the consumption of multiple types of TV programs, respondents were grouped into two categories: those who reported watching one to two types of programming ("Narrow TV Consumption"; N = 1,129) and those who reported watching three or more types ("Broad TV Consumption"; N = 1,368). These two groups reflected roughly equal halves of the sample among those who reported consuming at least one type of TV program.

2.2.3.2. Perceptions of Economic Inequality

Participants were asked, "In which domains or for which groups of people do you perceive inequalities in Britain?" (responses were limited to a maximum of three types of inequality). These included "income" and "wealth". Income inequality was the most commonly perceived form, reported by 34.4% of participants, followed by wealth inequality at 32.3%. Fewer than 1 in 20 participants reported perceiving no forms of inequality. A full distribution of responses is provided in appendix A.

2.2.3.3. Political Orientation

Participants self-reported their political orientation using the following prompt: "In political matters, people talk of 'the left' and 'the right.' How would you place your views on this scale, generally speaking?" The response was presented as a horizontal scale ranging from 0 (far left) to 10 (far right), with the two endpoints labelled accordingly. When asked to place themselves on this left-right ideological scale, responses clustered around the centre, with 24.2% selecting the midpoint (5). The next most common responses were in the 3-4 range (16.1%). Responses at the ideological extremes (0, 1, 9, and 10) were collectively selected by 13.8% of participants. For analysis, responses were grouped into three categories:

- (1) Left (values 0–3; coded as 1),
- (2) Centre (values 4–6; coded as 2),
- (3) Right (values 7–10; coded as 3).

Among the valid responses (N = 2,625), 22.0% were grouped as left-leaning (n = 659), 43.0% as centrist (n = 1,290), and 22.5% as right-leaning (n = 676). A total of 377 participants did not provide a valid response and were classified as system missing.

2.2.3.4. Party Affiliation

Participants were asked: *"Is there a particular political party you feel closer to than all the other parties?"* Those who answered "Yes" were then asked: *"Which party do you feel closer to?"*. Just over half of the sample (56.7%) reported feeling close to a particular political party, while 39.6% did not. Among those expressing party closeness, 21.7% identified with the Labour Party, 15.2% with the Conservative Party, 6.3% with the Brexit Party/Reform UK, 5.4% with the Green Party, and 4.7% with the Liberal Democrats. Smaller proportions reported affiliation with the Scottish National Party (2.0%), Plaid Cymru (0.3%), or another party (0.9%). Participants that identified with the Scottish National Party, Plaid Cymru, and Other were excluded from further analyses due to their small sample sizes. Additionally, "Can't choose" was combined with "I don't feel close to a party" to form a single "No Party Affiliation" category.

2.3. Newspaper Frequency Analysis & Qualitative Inspection

Examples of the TV programming types were used as keywords for a frequency analysis conducted annually across four media outlets. These outlets were organized according to a two-by-two typology reflecting political leaning (left vs. right) and format (tabloid vs. broadsheet), as shown in Table 2. Data were collected using *Nexis*, a news aggregator service, covering the period from January 1, 2005, to December 31, 2024. Keyword frequencies were normalized by the total number of articles published by each outlet in each year.

For analysis, we combined daily and Sunday editions of each publication (e.g., *The Daily Telegraph* and *The Sunday Telegraph*), as well as print and online versions (e.g., *Daily Mail* and *MailOnline*). The categorization of media outlets by political leaning and format is presented in Table 2. This classification is based on each outlet's historical support for political parties during general elections and follows the categorization used in the Reuters Institute survey (Newman et al., 2020).

Table 2: Categorisation of Newspaper Outlets by Political Orientation and Format

Newspaper Category	Publication Names	Political Orientation	Party Support	Format
Daily Mail / Mail on Sunday	The Daily Mail (London) (print); The Mail on Sunday (London) (print); MailOnline (digital)	Right	Conservative Party (2005–2024)	Tabloid
The Guardian / The Observer	The Guardian (London) (print); The Observer (print); theguardian.com (digital)	Left	Labour Party (1979–2001); 2005 Labour & Liberal Democrats; 2010 Liberal	Broadsheet

			Democrats; 2015 – 2024 Labour party	
Daily / Sunday Telegraph	The Daily Telegraph (print); The Sunday Telegraph (print); telegraph.co.uk (digital)	Right	Conservative Party (2005–2024)	Broadsheet
Daily / Sunday Mirror	The Daily Mirror (print); The Sunday Mirror (print); mirror.co.uk (digital)	Left	Labour Party (2005–2024)	Tabloid

Within the four newspaper categories listed in table 2, types of TV programming were searched using associated keywords. Each of the keywords were checked in Nexis, a news aggregator, to validate whether the search was specific to the TV Program intended. However, pilot testing revealed that some programme names were too general to yield accurate or relevant results. For instance, the keyword *Teachers*—used to represent fictional dramas about ineffective government and welfare systems—returned many unrelated articles referring broadly to the education sector, rather than the specific TV programme. Similarly, the keyword *The Lottery Winners* was removed after we found it referred to a wide array of shows (e.g., *My Lottery Dream Home*) rather than a single identifiable title. Fictional dramas about the elite and their families were also excluded from the final analysis. Programme titles such as *Elite*, *The Crown*, and *Succession* produced ambiguous or overly general results, leading to an unreliable category. Such ambiguous terms were excluded from the final keyword set. A complete list of keyword searches used is provided in table 3.

Table 3: Table of Keywords by TV Programming Type.

TV Program Type	Key words searched
Real-life Stories of Everyday Individuals Achieving Success	"The Apprentice" OR "The 1% Club" OR "Dragons' Den" OR "X-Factor" OR "The Voice"
Real-life Stories of Individuals Finding Unexpected Wealth	"Cash in the Attic" OR "Antiques Roadshow"
Real-life Stories of the Everyday Heroes Workers in the Public Sector	"Educating Essex" OR "24 Hours in A&E"
Fictional Dramas About an Ineffective Government and Welfare System	"The Job Lot" OR "The Thick of It" OR "Yes Minister"
Real-life Stories of the Everyday Heroes in the Private Sector	"The Secret Millionaire" OR "Undercover Boss"
Real-life Stories About the Differences in Income and Wealth Between Families	"Rich House, Poor House" OR "How the Other Half Lives" OR "Rich Holiday, Poor Holiday"
Real-life Stories of Everyday Individuals Living in Poverty and/or on Welfare Payments	"Breadline Britain" OR "Benefits Street" OR "Jeremy Kyle"
Real-life Stories of the Everyday Lives of Rich Individuals	"Keeping Up with the Kardashians" OR "The Real Housewives"

To further enrich the interpretation, four TV programming types were selected for qualitative inspection. These four types were identified through factor analysis, as described in the results section (Section 3.4). From component 1—the component that included the largest number of TV programming

types—two examples were selected. One example was selected from each of the remaining components. This selection is detailed in section 3.12.

The qualitative inspection considered formatting and narrative features of the articles, including the title, main body text, and accompanying images. Attention was given to the tone and framing of the coverage to gain a sense of how each programme was being represented. The time frame for this qualitative analysis was narrowed to years when the programme type was particularly salient, as detailed in table 11.

We relate findings suggested in the qualitative analysis to consumption patterns and individual differences in economic inequality perceptions and political orientations and party affiliations found in the quantitative analysis. This inspection also considered how representations may have been politicised or socialised. Specifically, we examined whether the programmes were framed in ways that were explicitly critical of economic inequality or the poor, whether they portrayed such issues in a neutral or humorous manner, and whether any notable differences emerged across media categorized by political orientation (left vs. right) and format (tabloid vs. broadsheet) within the selected time periods. Additionally, attention was given to how coherently the selected TV programme examples aligned with their respective category types. This helped assess whether the examples consistently reflected the intended themes of each category.

Measures of quality in qualitative analysis are dialogical in basis (Flick, 2018), aiming to build confidence in interpretations through thorough engagement with the sociological imagination (Provencher, 2011). They enable the construction of a fuller account by allowing comparisons with quantitative results. The focus is on the depth of interpretation, while also offering a measure of internal reliability—particularly regarding the variability within types of television programming measured in the survey instrument (Flick, 2018).

3. Results

This results section is structured as follows. First, we present the consumption patterns of television programming types surveyed in 2024, with attention to variability in socio-demographic factors, the breadth of programming types consumed, and a factor analysis of within-individual constellations of typical multiple-consumption covariance patterns. Next, we examine possible correlations between the consumption of television programming types and the recognition of income and wealth inequality as one of the top three inequality issues in Britain. This includes associations with differences in political orientation and party affiliation, analysed according to both specific programming types and the overall breadth of programming consumption. Following an interim summary, we focus on the reception of four television programming types in digital and print media from 2005 to 2024. These four types were selected to vary along dimensions of media outlet political affiliation and party support, as well as publication format (broadsheet vs. tabloid). This section considers both the relative salience of these programming types in media coverage and, qualitatively, the nature of their reception, including implications for politicization.

3.1. Consumption of types of TV Programming

Participants' self-reported consumption of various types of television programs—either recently or in the past—on any device or service was first examined. Responses to the television program types surveyed ranged from 17.7% to 58.2%, indicating a diverse array of cultural narratives concerning economic inequality (table 1). These narratives depicted various social groups and contexts perceived to contribute to, maintain, or depend upon the mechanisms by which income and wealth are generated, as well as those reliant on state-based systems. The most consumed content, reported by over half the sample, was real-life stories of everyday individuals achieving success, such as 'The Apprentice' (table 1). The least commonly consumed content was real-life stories of wealthy individuals, exemplified by programs such as *The Real Housewives* (table 1).

3.2. Socio-Demographic variations in consumption of types of TV Programming

As part of our analysis, we also explored associations between socio-demographic variables and TV programme type consumption, highlighting that not all programme types were consumed equally across the sample (see Table 4). Gender was modelled as a binary variable (male/female). Age was categorised into five groups: 18–24 years, 25–34 years, 35–49 years, 50–64 years, and 65–99 years. Household income was divided into ten bands, ranging from less than £1,014 per month (lowest band) to more than £6,063 per month (highest band). Education was grouped according to years of schooling: (1) those who left school at the minimum compulsory age (typically around age 16 in the UK, equivalent to GCSE-level qualifications); (2) those who completed some additional secondary education (e.g., AS- or A-levels); (3) those with some form of tertiary education (e.g., bachelor’s degree or equivalent); and (4) those with postgraduate qualifications. Individuals who selected ‘other’ or ‘can’t choose’ were excluded from the analysis.

Table 4: Chi-Square Significance Testing of TV Programming Type by Socio-Demographic Variables

TV Programme Type	Gender (χ^2 , p)	Age (χ^2 , p)	Household Income (χ^2 , p)	Education Level (χ^2 , p)
Real-life Stories of Everyday Individuals Achieving Success	$\chi^2(1) = 37.45$, p = 0.951	$\chi^2(4) = 43.19$, p = 0.291	$\chi^2(9) = 30.46$, p = 0.098	$\chi^2(3) = 59.79$, p = 0.922
Real-life Stories of Individuals Finding Unexpected Wealth	$\chi^2(1) = 73.2$, p = 0.599	$\chi^2(4) = 61.19$, p = 0.139	$\chi^2(9) = 68.42$, p = 0.44	$\chi^2(3) = 8.85$, p = 0.196
Real-life Stories of Individuals Living in Poverty and/or on Welfare	$\chi^2(1) = 15.6$, p = 0.156	$\chi^2(4) = 29.21$, p = 0.366	$\chi^2(9) = 12.2$, p = 0.495	$\chi^2(3) = 4.52$, p = 0.325
Real-life Stories About Differences in Income and Wealth Between Families	$\chi^2(1) = 5.81$, p = 0.866	$\chi^2(4) = 45.61$, p = 0.785	$\chi^2(9) = 3.44$, p = 0.909	$\chi^2(3) = 38.87$, p = 0.271
Real-life Stories of Everyday Heroes in the Private Sector	$\chi^2(1) = 60.11$, p = 0.708	$\chi^2(4) = 19.97$, p = 0.514	$\chi^2(9) = 25.88$, p = 0.663	$\chi^2(3) = 82.87$, p = 0.357
Real-life Stories of Everyday Heroes in the Public Sector	$\chi^2(1) = 2.06$, p = 0.97	$\chi^2(4) = 59.24$, p = 0.046	$\chi^2(9) = 31.17$, p = 0.52	$\chi^2(3) = 28.09$, p = 0.543
Fictional Dramas About an Ineffective Government and Welfare System	$\chi^2(1) = 83.24$, p = 0.212	$\chi^2(4) = 60.75$, p = 0.171	$\chi^2(9) = 54.67$, p = 0.185	$\chi^2(3) = 14.09$, p = 0.802
Fictional Dramas About the Elite and Their Families	$\chi^2(1) = 18.18$, p = 0.183	$\chi^2(4) = 6.51$, p = 0.949	$\chi^2(9) = 96.96$, p = 0.775	$\chi^2(3) = 7.46$, p = 0.987
Real-life Stories of the Everyday Lives of Rich Individuals	$\chi^2(1) = 30.42$, p = 0.525	$\chi^2(4) = 96.56$, p = 0.808	$\chi^2(9) = 93.95$, p = 0.895	$\chi^2(3) = 77.22$, p = 0.199

Chi-square tests of independence revealed that the only statistically significant association was between age group and interest in *Real-life Stories of Everyday Heroes in the Public Sector*, $\chi^2(4, N = 2488) = 59.24$, $p = .046$.

3.3. Breadth in consumption of types of TV Programming

The breadth of TV programming types containing narratives relevant to the comprehension of economic inequality was also explored. Participants were categorized into two groups based on their reported viewing: those who had watched one to two types of programming were classified as having a narrow consumption, while those who had watched three to nine types were classified as having broad consumption.

Graph 1: Cumulative Breadth of Self-Reported Consumption of TV Programming Types.

Cumulative Frequency of Self-Reported Consumption of TV Programming Types

Approximately one-fifth of participants reported consumption of only one type (graph 1). Roughly half the sample (45.2%) reported consuming between one-to-two types of television programming (graph 1). Additionally, 11.8% of respondents reported consumption of six or more types (graph 1), indicating a subset of individuals engaging with a broad range of narratives related to economic inequality.

3.4. Within-individual correlations in consumption of types of TV Programming

The Pearson correlation matrix revealed a range of low to moderate associations between different types of TV programming consumption (Appendix B).

To examine whether there were within-individual patterns in the types of TV programming consumed, we conducted an Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) using Principal Component Analysis (PCA) based on the correlational matrix (table 5). An Oblimin rotation (which allows factors to correlate) was applied to account for conceptual overlap between different types of content.

Preliminary checks indicated that the data were suitable for factor analysis. The sample size was large ($N = 2,497$), the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measure of sampling adequacy was .740, and Bartlett's test of sphericity was statistically significant, $\chi^2(36) = 1849.48$, $p < .001$. These results confirmed that the item covariances were strong enough to justify factor analysis.

Table 5: Communalities for TV Programming Types Extracted via Principal Component Analysis

TV Programming Type	Extraction
Fictional Dramas About an Ineffective Government and Welfare System:	0.733
Fictional Dramas About the Elite and Their Families	0.665
Real-life Stories of Everyday Individuals Finding Unexpected Wealth:	0.603
Real-life Stories of the Everyday Lives of Rich Individuals	0.519
Real-life Stories About the Differences in Income and Wealth Between Families	0.491
Real-life Stories of Everyday Individuals Living in Poverty and /or on Welfare Payments	0.465
Real-life Stories of the Everyday Heroes in the Private Sector	0.439
Real-life Stories of the Everyday Heroes Workers in the Public Sector	0.308
Real-life Stories of Everyday Individuals Achieving Success:	0.295

As shown in table 5, the communality scores suggest that some television programming types were more distinct. For example, Fictional Dramas About Government and the Welfare System had a high extraction score of .733, and Fictional Dramas About the Elite and Their Families scored .665. In contrast, others demonstrated weaker or borderline fits, such as Real-life Stories of Everyday Individuals Achieving Success, which had a low communality of .295. Three components with eigenvalues greater than 1.0 were extracted, accounting for 50.18% of the variance (table 6).

Table 6. Component Variance

Component	Eigenvalue	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	2.267	25.19%	25.19%
2	1.164	12.94%	38.12%
3	1.085	12.05%	50.18%

Table 7. Pattern Matrix of TV Programming Consumption Types (Oblimin Rotation; values <0.4 suppressed for visualisation)

TV Program Type	Component 1	Component 2	Component 3
Real-life Stories About the Differences in Income and Wealth Between Families	0.698		
Real-life Stories of Everyday Individuals Living in Poverty and/or on Welfare Payments	0.661		
Real-life Stories of the Everyday Heroes in the Private Sector	0.634		
Real-life Stories of the Everyday Heroes Workers in the Public Sector	0.547		
Real-life Stories of Everyday Individuals Achieving Success	0.519		

Fictional Dramas About an Ineffective Government and Welfare System		0.739	
Fictional Dramas About the Elite and Their Families		0.721	
Real-life Stories of Everyday Individuals Finding Unexpected Wealth			0.678
Real-life Stories of the Everyday Lives of Rich Individuals			-.563

An examination of the components of TV programming types (table 7) suggests that individuals' consumption preferences may, in part, reflect distinctions between dramatized real-life stories and fictional dramas—though we acknowledge that this distinction is somewhat heuristic. For example, Component 1 encompasses programming such as Real-life Stories About the Differences in Income and Wealth Between Families, which often adopts a docuseries format to selectively compare the experiences of those living in poverty versus those living in wealth. Similarly, Real-life Stories of Everyday Individuals Living in Poverty and/or on Welfare Payments (e.g., Breadline Britain) follows a comparable format, although comparisons are more implicitly made through the voiceover or narrative framing, encouraging the audience to evaluate the social beneficiaries depicted. Across these formats, there is a common focus on the affective and moral experiences of individuals navigating real personal struggles within broader societal contexts.

In contrast, Component 2 (table 7), which includes the highest factor loadings—Fictional Dramas About an Ineffective Government and Welfare System (loading = .739) and Fictional Dramas About the Elite and Their Families (loading = .721)—represents a shift from 'real-life' storytelling to fictional dramatizations (table 7). These narratives differ in that they often satirize or critique institutional and elite dynamics, as seen in shows like *The Job Lot* vs *Succession*. Notably, in the U.S. context, both civil servants and ultra-wealthy families are often perceived as part of the broader elite (Condon & Wichowsky, 2020).

Component 3 includes Real-life Stories of Everyday Individuals Finding Unexpected Wealth (loading = .678) and Real-life Stories of the Everyday Lives of Rich Individuals (loading = -.563) (table 7). Although these items load in opposite directions, they share a thematic focus on "looking upward." On one side, programs such as *Cash in the Attic* depict ordinary individuals coming into wealth unexpectedly, while on the other, shows like *Keeping Up with the Kardashians* portray the everyday lives of the ultra-rich. Despite differences in tone and perceived accessibility, both types of content may offer viewers a sense of what is aspirational or attainable.

This may suggest that patterns of TV programming consumption align not only with a reality–fiction distinction, but also with how narratives frame social position and mobility—whether focusing on hardship ("looking down") or aspiration ("looking up"). However, given the variability in communality scores and challenges in interpretation of components—as well as the opposing directions of the factor loadings in component 3—further analysis will focus on individual TV programme types rather than components. However, these components were used to sub-sample of programme types for the subsequent qualitative inspection (see section 3.12).

3.5. Associations between self-reported presence of income and wealth inequality in Britain (Top 3 perceived inequalities) and television programming consumption types.

The relationship between self-reported television programme consumption and the perception of economic inequality as one of the top three forms of inequality in Britain was explored using a series of chi-square tests of independence. These analyses evaluated whether viewers of specific content types were more likely to report perceiving income or wealth inequality. Participants from the original sample (N = 3,002) were excluded from the analysis if they selected "Can't choose" in response to any of the following items: perception of income inequality in Britain, perception of wealth inequality in Britain,

or television programming consumption. This resulted in sub-sample of 2,416 respondents. Chi-square tests were conducted to examine associations between self-reported consumption of TV Programming types and presence perceptions of two inequality types, wealth and income (yes vs. no)(table 8).

Table 8: Odds Ratios and Significance Tests for TV Media Consumption × Inequality Perceptions (Uncorrected and Bonferroni-Adjusted Significance Reporting)

TV Media Type	Income Inequality OR [95% CI]	<i>P</i> <0.05	Wealth Inequality OR [95% CI]	<i>P</i> <0.05
Real-life Stories of Everyday Individuals Achieving Success	1.05 [1.24]	[.89,	1.07 [.90, 1.27]	0.456
Real-life Stories of Individuals Finding Unexpected Wealth	1.07 [1.26]	[.90,	0.90 [.75, 1.06]	0.203
Real-life Stories of Individuals Living in Poverty/Welfare	1.23 [1.47]	[1.03,	1.10 [.91, 1.32]	0.321
Income and Wealth Differences Between Families	1.16 [1.39]	[.97,	1.22 [1.02, 1.47]	0.031
Everyday Heroes in the Private Sector	1.10 [1.31]	[.91,	1.26 [1.05, 1.51]	0.013
Everyday Heroes in the Public Sector	1.11 [1.31]	[.94,	1.08 [.91, 1.28]	0.391
Fictional Dramas about Government/Welfare Inefficiency	1.12 [1.33]	[.94,	1.16 [.98, 1.39]	0.091
Fictional Dramas about the Elite and Their Families	1.16 [1.37]	[.98,	1.25 [1.05, 1.48]	0.012
Real-life Stories of Rich Individuals	0.98 [1.22]	[.79,	1.23 [.99, 1.53]	0.061

Note. Bolded values indicate statistical significance at the uncorrected $p < .05$ level. None of the comparisons remained statistically significant after Bonferroni correction (adjusted $\alpha = .0028$). OR = Odds Ratio; CI = Confidence Interval.

Among the nine TV programming types assessed, only one — *Real-life Stories of Individuals Living in Poverty/Welfare* — showed a statistically significant association at the conventional level, $\chi^2(1) = 5.02$, $p = .025$, with a Mantel-Haenszel odds ratio (OR) of 1.23, 95% CI [1.03, 1.47]. This indicates a 23% higher likelihood of perceiving income inequality among those who reported consuming this content. However, when applying a Bonferroni correction to account for multiple testing (18 tests; corrected $\alpha = .0028$), this result was no longer statistically significant. No other media types demonstrated significant associations with income inequality perceptions at either the uncorrected or corrected level ($p > .05$).

A similar pattern emerged in the analysis of perceived wealth inequality. Three types of media content were significantly associated with wealth inequality perceptions at the conventional level ($p < .05$):

- *Income and Wealth Differences Between Families*, $\chi^2(1) = 4.65, p = .031, OR = 1.22, 95\% CI [1.02, 1.47]$
- *Everyday Heroes in the Private Sector*, $\chi^2(1) = 6.22, p = .013, OR = 1.26, 95\% CI [1.05, 1.51]$
- *Fictional Dramas about the Elite and Their Families*, $\chi^2(1) = 6.37, p = .012, OR = 1.25, 95\% CI [1.05, 1.48]$

These results suggest that individuals who consumed these content types were more likely to perceive wealth inequality. However, none of these associations met the Bonferroni-corrected threshold for significance ($p < .0028$), suggesting a high risk for Type 1 errors. The remaining media types did not show significant relationships with wealth inequality perceptions at either threshold.

3.6. Associations between self-reported presence of income and wealth inequality in Britain (Top 3 perceived inequalities) and breadth of television programming consumption types.

We explored whether the presence of economic inequality perceptions differed according to the breadth of types of television programming consumption. A chi-square test revealed a statistically significant association between breadth of TV media consumption and perceived wealth inequality, $\chi^2(1) = 10.69, p = .001$. Specifically, 59.4% of broad-TV consumption respondents perceived wealth inequality, compared to 40.6% of narrow-consumption respondents. The Mantel-Haenszel odds ratio was 1.33, 95% CI [1.12, 1.58], indicating that respondents in the broad TV consumption group were 33% more likely to perceive wealth inequality in Britain than those with narrower media exposure.

In contrast, the association between TV consumption and perceived income inequality was not statistically significant, $\chi^2(1) = 2.82, p = .093$. The Mantel-Haenszel odds ratio was 1.15, 95% CI [0.98, 1.36], indicating no meaningful difference in perceived income inequality between broad and narrow TV consumption groups.

3.7. Associations between Political Orientation and TV Programming Types Consumption.

To explore whether political orientation was associated with the consumption of television programming that featured narratives relevant to economic inequality, a series of chi-square tests of independence were conducted.

Table 9: Grouped political orientated correlations with TV media Type

TV Media Type	Chi-square (df=2)	p-value	Phi
Real-life Stories of Everyday Individuals Achieving Success	0.05	0.973	0.005
Real-life Stories of Individuals Finding Unexpected Wealth	19.09	<.001	0.093
Real-life Stories of Individuals Living in Poverty/Welfare	0.48	0.787	0.015
Income and Wealth Differences Between Families	4.22	0.121	0.044
Everyday Heroes in the Private Sector	1.41	0.495	0.025
Everyday Heroes in the Public Sector	15.93	<.001	0.085
Fictional Dramas about Government/Welfare Inefficiency	31.01	<.001	0.118

Fictional Dramas about the Elite and Their Families	26.17	<.001	0.109
Real-life Stories of Rich Individuals	0.5	0.781	0.015

Note. Bolded values indicate statistical significance at the uncorrected $p < .05$ level.

Across the nine programming categories analysed, significant associations emerged for four tv programming types under the conventional alpha level of .05 (table 9). Specifically, political orientation was significantly associated with consumption of the following:

- Real-life stories of individuals finding unexpected wealth, $\chi^2(2, N = 2,216) = 19.09, p < .001, \Phi = .093$. Right-leaning individuals reported greater consumption (50.8%) relative to those on the left (38.0%).
- Everyday heroes in the public sector, $\chi^2(2, N = 2,216) = 15.93, p < .001, \Phi = .085$. Left-leaning respondents reported higher levels of consumption (40.9%) compared to their right-leaning counterparts (33.7%).
- Fictional dramas about government or welfare inefficiency, $\chi^2(2, N = 2,216) = 31.01, p < .001, \Phi = .118$. Left-leaning participants were the most frequent viewers (46.4%) relative to centrists (32.5%) and right-leaning individuals (35.6%).
- Fictional dramas about the elite and their families, $\chi^2(2, N = 2,216) = 26.17, p < .001, \Phi = .109$. Viewership was highest among left-leaning respondents (48.4%) and lowest among those on the right (34.0%).

To account for multiple comparisons, a Bonferroni correction was applied to adjust the significance threshold ($\alpha = .05 / 9 = .0056$). After correction, three associations remained statistically significant: real-life stories of individuals finding unexpected wealth; fictional dramas about government or welfare inefficiency; and fictional dramas about the elite and their families. The relationship between political orientation and consumption of everyday heroes in the public sector, while significant under the uncorrected threshold, did not meet the Bonferroni-adjusted criterion.

3.8. Associations Between Self-Reported Political Orientation Inequality and Breadth of Television Programming Consumption

To explore whether political orientation was associated with the breadth of television programming consumption related to economic inequality, a chi-square test of independence was conducted, using previously set out categorisations. The chi-square analysis revealed no statistically significant association between political orientation and breadth of television consumption, $\chi^2(2, N = 2,216) = 1.18, p = .553$.

3.9. Associations between Self-Reported Party Affiliation and TV Programming Types Consumption.

A series of chi-square tests were conducted to assess whether consumption of TV programming types varied significantly by political party affiliation. Table 10 summarizes the results, and adjusted standardized residuals (ASRs) are reported for cells with significant deviations from expected frequencies to understand which political parties explain variance. We found that five of the nine TV programming types were significantly associated with political party affiliation at the $p < .05$ level. Given the number of comparisons conducted, a Bonferroni correction was also applied to reduce the risk of Type I error across the nine TV content categories (adjusted $\alpha = .05 / 9 = .0056$). With the Bonferroni correction, only 3 of the nine TV programming types were significant.

Table 10: Chi-Square Test Results for Political Party Affiliation by TV Media Type Consumption.

TV Media Type	χ^2 (df)	p	Cramér's V	Significant ASRs ($ ASR \geq 1.96$)
Real-life Stories of Everyday Individuals Achieving Success	7.59 (6)	0.27	0.055	None
Real-life Stories of Individuals Finding Unexpected Wealth	34.55 (6)	<.001	0.118	Conservative (+4.5), No Affiliation (-4.7)
Real-life Stories of Individuals Living in Poverty and/or on Welfare Payments	22.75 (6)	<.001	0.095	Labour (+3.3), Conservative (-3.8)
Real-life Stories About the Differences in Income and Wealth Between Families	9.97 (6)	0.126	0.063	Conservative (-2.1) †
Real-life Stories of the Everyday Heroes in the Private Sector	1.23 (6)	0.975	0.022	None
Real-life Stories of the Everyday Heroes Workers in the Public Sector	16.29 (6)	0.012	0.081	Conservative (-3.1), Lib Dem (+2.5)
Fictional Dramas About an Ineffective Government and Welfare System	38.66 (6)	<.001	0.124	Lib Dem (+3.6), Green (+2.6), No Affiliation (-4.7)
Fictional Dramas About the Elite and Their Families	7.92 (6)	0.244	0.056	None
Real-life Stories of the Everyday Lives of Rich Individuals	33.08 (6)	<.001	0.115	Conservative (-3.8), Green (+3.7)

We found that there was a significant association between political affiliation and consumption of Real-life Stories of Individuals Finding Unexpected Wealth, $\chi^2(6, N = 2,497) = 34.55, p < .001, \Phi = .118$. Conservative voters expressed greater-than-expected interest (ASR = +4.5), while unaffiliated respondents reported significantly less interest than expected (ASR = -4.7). This remained significant with Bonferroni correction.

Real-life Stories of Individuals Living in Poverty and/or on Welfare was also significantly associated with political affiliation, $\chi^2(6, N = 2,497) = 22.75, p < .001, \Phi = .095$. Labour supporters were overrepresented among interested viewers (ASR = +3.3), whereas Conservative voters were underrepresented (ASR = -3.8). This remained significant with Bonferroni correction.

The chi-square test for Real-life Stories About Differences in Income and Wealth Between Families approached significance but did not meet the adjusted threshold, $\chi^2(6, N = 2,497) = 9.97, p = .126, \Phi = .063$. Conservatives reported marginally less interest than expected (ASR = -2.1), but this did not remain significant after correction for multiple comparisons.

A statistically significant association was also found for Real-life Stories of Everyday Heroes in the Public Sector, $\chi^2(6, N = 2,497) = 16.29, p = .012, \Phi = .081$. Liberal Democrat viewers showed greater-than-expected interest (ASR = +2.5), while Conservatives were less likely to express interest (ASR = -3.1).

Consumers of Real-life Stories of the Everyday Lives of Rich Individuals showed a strong association with political affiliation, $\chi^2(6, N = 2,497) = 33.08, p < .001, \Phi = .115$. Green Party voters were significantly overrepresented among viewers of this content (ASR = +3.7), and Conservatives were significantly underrepresented (ASR = -3.8). This remained significant with Bonferroni correction.

3.10. Associations between Self-Reported Party Affiliation and Breadth of TV Programming Types Consumption.

To assess whether the breadth of consumption of television content related to economic inequality differed by political party affiliation, a chi-square test of independence was conducted. This test examined whether the breadth of television consumption scores varied across self-reported political affiliations, including participants with no party affiliation. The analysis revealed no statistically significant association between political affiliation and breadth of television content consumption, $\chi^2(48, N = 2,497) = 54.28, p = .247, \text{Cramér's } V = .060$

3.11. Interim Results Summary.

The analysis revealed that television programming featuring narratives related to economic inequality was widely consumed, with 83.2% of respondents reporting having viewed at least one of the listed program types. The most consumed programming types were *Real-life Stories of Everyday Individuals Achieving Success* (58.2%), *Real-life Stories of Individuals Finding Unexpected Wealth* (42.7%), and *Real-life Stories of Everyday Heroes in the Public Sector* (41.5%). The least consumed content type was *Real-life Stories of the Everyday Lives of Rich Individuals* (17.7%). There was partial evidence consumption of TV programming types may partially load on to 3 latent components.

There was notable variation in the breadth of consumption. Approximately one-fifth of participants reported viewing only one type of programme, whereas over half of the sample reported having consumed more than two types of tv programming types. Breadth of consumption was significantly associated with perceived wealth inequality. In addition, consumption of *Income and Wealth Differences Between Families*, *Everyday Heroes in the Private Sector*, and *Fictional Dramas About the Elite and Their Families* were all associated with perceptions of wealth inequality at the uncorrected level ($p < .05$). Real-life television stories about people living in poverty or on welfare were likewise associated with perceptions of income inequality, also at the uncorrected level ($p < .05$)

A series of chi-square tests revealed several significant associations between political orientation and patterns of television consumption. We found that participants who reported watching *Real-life Stories of Individuals Finding Unexpected Wealth* was more frequently consumed by right-leaning individuals than left-leaning individuals, and by Conservative Party supporters relative to other affiliations. Viewers of *real-life stories of individuals living in poverty or on welfare* were more likely to be Labour supporters, while Conservatives showed less consumption with this type of programming. Left leaning and liberal Democrat viewers had higher levels of consumption of *real-life stories of everyday heroes in the public sector*, while Conservatives again had lower consumption of this TV programming type. A strong association also emerged between political orientation and interest in stories about the everyday lives of rich individuals, with Green Party voters overrepresented among viewers, and Conservatives underrepresented. Consumption of *Fictional dramas about government or welfare inefficiency* and *Fictional dramas about the elite and their families* were more common in left-leaning participants.

3.12. Qualitative Inspection.

As shown in table 8, individual differences revealed covariances in the types of TV programming consumed, partially suggesting a three-factor solution. Five TV programming types loaded onto Component 1, and two loaded onto each of the other two components. We selected media outlets based on the factor loadings: the two highest-loading TV programming types for Component 1 (as it included five TV programs), and the highest-loading TV programming types for each of Components 2 and 3 respectively.

For Component 1, we focus on two example TV programming types: ‘Real-life Stories About the Differences in Income and Wealth Between Families’; and ‘Real-life Stories of Everyday Individuals Living in Poverty and/or on Welfare Payments’. For Component 2, the example selected was: ‘Fictional Dramas About an Ineffective Government and Welfare System’. For Component 3, the example selected was: ‘Real-life Stories of Everyday Individuals Finding Unexpected Wealth’.

We explored the relative salience of these TV programming type examples in four newspapers, analysed by two dimensions: political orientation (left vs. right) and format (broadsheet vs. tabloid). Details of these searches are included in Table 11 and the frequencies shown are normalised to the total number of articles per year of each outlet in the news aggregator Nexis. We consider how the representation of the TV programmes and their implications for politicisation may relate to the political orientation of the newspaper selected as well as the format type.

Years of qualitative inspection are shown in Table 11; these years were selected for each news outlet and television programming type based on variations in peak coverage described in sections 3.13 – 3.16.

Table 11: Years of Qualitative Inspection by News Outlet and TV Programming Type

TV Programming Type	Telegraph	Guardian	Daily Mirror	Daily Mail
Real-life Stories About the Differences in Income and Wealth Between Families	2015– 2017	2017– 2019	2020– 2022	2016– 2019
Real-life Stories of Everyday Individuals Living in Poverty and/or on Welfare Payments	2013– 2015	2013– 2015	2014– 2016	2013– 2015
Fictional Dramas About an Ineffective Government and Welfare System	2012– 2014	2009– 2014	2012– 2014	2012– 2014
Real-life Stories of Everyday Individuals Finding Unexpected Wealth	2009– 2013	2009– 2015	2015– 2019	2011– 2015

3.13. Real-life Stories About the Differences in Income and Wealth Between Families

This category focuses on real-life television programmes that explore lifestyle contrasts between families from opposite ends of the economic spectrum—examples include *How the Other Half Lives*, *Rich House, Poor House*, and *Rich Holiday, Poor Holiday*. *How the Other Half Lives* aired from 2015 to 2018; *Rich House, Poor House* has run from 2017 to the present, and its spin-off, *Rich Holiday, Poor Holiday*, has aired from 2020 to the present. These shows typically follow a format of temporary “life swaps” between wealthy and low-income families, aiming to provoke emotional responses through striking contrasts.

Approximately one-third of respondents who reported their TV consumption selected this programme type. These individuals were more likely to associate with the Conservative Party and to rank wealth inequality among the top three issues they perceived in Britain. However, while neither of these effects remained statistically significant after corrections for multiple testing, we describe below how this category of TV programmes includes both symbols of wealth and explicit references to wealth inequality. Furthermore, greater consideration of these themes is observed in right-leaning newspapers compared to left-leaning ones, across both tabloid and broadsheet formats.

Graph 2: Relative Salience of ‘ Income and Wealth Differences Between Families’ in British Newspapers (2015–2024)

Income and wealth differences between families e.g., "Rich House, Poor House" OR "How the Other Half Lives" OR "Rich Holiday, Poor Holiday"

As shown in graph 2, coverage across outlets first peaked between 2016 and 2019—especially in the *Daily Mail*, which offered the most sustained engagement—and rose again from 2020 (graph 2). Other outlets surveyed covered the shows more sporadically (graph 2) and with notably different tones. Relatively higher levels of consideration for these TV media types are found in the tabloid press compared to broadsheets, and in right-wing outlets relative to those on the political left (graph 2).

On the political right, the tabloid *Daily Mail* portrayed the most vivid and emotionally framed accounts. In one feature, a millionaire family with “a Porsche, a Range Rover and [...] a rather splendid Bentley” swapped lives with a single mother’s family surviving on £138 a week. The article detailed how the wealthy daughter, who “spends £300 a week on clothes,” was mortified to clean a stranger’s toilet, while the working-class mother described living rich as “being on an all-inclusive holiday.” The piece ends with the moving reflection that, for some, wealth meant not dreading the postman because “he’s always bringing bills” (*Daily Mail*, 25 March 2017). Another article praised the generosity of a wealthy couple who, after participating in the show, paid off a working family’s £11,000 in credit card debt—an act described as “an extraordinarily generous thing to do” (*Daily Mail*, 5 May 2018).

In contrast, engagement in *The Daily Telegraph* and *The Sunday Telegraph*—also on the political right—ranged from neutral presentation to criticism. One listing neutrally described the show: “Rich House, Poor House CHANNEL 5, 9.00PM. This series in which contrasting families swap homes for a week gets a deserved second series. It begins with the Leamon family from Southampton who live on £170 a week switching homes with the Fiddes from Royal Wootton Bassett, who own a plush six-bedroom house and live on a weekly budget of £1,500” (*The Daily Telegraph*, 19 October 2017). Another article critiqued the format as voyeuristic: “Rich House, Poor House CHANNEL 5, 9.00PM? Where once it was the home of late-night erotica, Channel 5 now has a new obsession—poverty, with shows such as *Benefits by the Sea: Jaywick dominating its schedules*. In this prurient new series, rich and poor families swap lives for a week” (*The Daily Telegraph*, 30 March 2017).

Image 1: Review of *Rich House, Poor House* in The Guardian Newspaper (2018)

Review

Rich House, Poor House review - an overly reassuring tale of the Haves and Have Nots

Anyone looking for insights into the injustices of wealth inequality will have been left shortchanged by a feelgood reality show marred by a poverty of imagination

Meet the Haves: the Coleman family, who swapped places with the Morgans. Photograph: Channel 5

Consideration of this type of TV programming in *The Guardian* never reached the same levels as in the *Daily Mail*. Mentions of the shows were brief and detached, with a tone of critique. The paper treated the programmes as overly simplistic in their portrayal of wealth inequality. For example, in a 2018 review, *The Guardian* described *Rich House, Poor House* as “an overly reassuring tale of the Haves and Have Nots,” arguing that anyone looking for deeper insight into injustice would be “left shortchanged” (*The Guardian*, 4 October 2018) (image 1). The implied ‘feel-good’ nature of the programme was contrasted with what *The Guardian* suggests is the ‘true’ nature of wealth inequality, rendering these curated comparisons between rich and poor lives not worthy of serious consideration.

The Mirror mostly focused on programming reminders but did highlight some storylines from *Rich House, Poor House*, particularly in the 2020s. By 2022, the show had entered political commentary. One reader’s letter, published during the cost-of-living crisis, suggested that politicians should appear on the programme to “swap with people who are really struggling to keep their heads above water,” adding that only then “might they be aware of how the other half live and struggle” (*Daily Mirror*, 18 July 2022). This suggests that, when considered, the show was referenced in relation to class relations and political distrust.

Across the newspapers surveyed, we find consistency in representations of cost-of-living differences, often centring on status symbols of wealth such as luxury housing, cars, and clothing. This may relate to heightened perceptions of wealth inequality in Britain, as well as a greater focus on perceived extreme social groups, such as “millionaire families” versus “the poor,” particularly in the right-leaning tabloid press. This pattern may also relate to the greater likelihood of association with the Conservative Party among viewers. However, we also observe differences in reception along lines of what is held up as valid sources of truth. In tabloid newspapers, the affective experiences of those depicted are treated as valid insight into wealth inequalities. In contrast, these experiences are largely rejected in broadsheet coverage, where they are implied to be an *annoyance*, either as voyeuristic obsession with poverty or as a false account of wealth inequality.

3.14. Real-life Stories of Everyday Individuals Living in Poverty and/or on Welfare Payments

This category centres on real-life television that depicts the lives of people, largely reliant on social benefits, living in poverty. Notable examples include *Benefits Street*, *Breadline Britain*, and *The Jeremy Kyle Show*—all of which brought these individuals into the public eye, albeit with very different tones and approaches. 29% of those who reported their TV consumption types selected this programming type.

As described previously, viewers of this type of TV programming were also more likely to identify income inequality as a major issue. This association reached statistical significance at $p < .05$; however, it did not remain significant after applying a Bonferroni correction ($p < .0028$). Paralleling this finding, as will be described below, although reception varied across outlets, all news sources addressed income-related issues—whether through the lens of paid employment or reliance on social benefits. Individuals who reported consuming this type of programming were also more likely to affiliate with the Labour Party and less likely to support the Conservative Party. This association remained statistically significant after Bonferroni correction, likely reflecting the more sympathetic and critical reception of these programmes in left-leaning outlets, particularly *The Guardian*.

Graph 3: Relative Salience of 'Real-life Stories of Everyday Individuals Living in Poverty and/or on Welfare Payments' in British Newspapers (2005–2024)

Overall, the highest levels of engagement with this type of TV programming were found in *The Guardian*, with peaks first occurring between 2010 and 2011, and again in 2014 (Graph 3). However, this genre was a more sustained feature of the tabloid press, particularly in *The Daily Mirror* and *The Daily Mail*, with the latter showing greater overall coverage, especially on the political right (Graph 3). That said, this pattern was not consistent across the right-leaning press, as coverage in *The Telegraph* newspapers remained relatively muted throughout the period (Graph 3). Qualitative inspection revealed that *The Jeremy Kyle Show* was referenced consistently in media coverage, though less prominently than other programmes. In contrast, coverage of *Breadline Britain* was more limited. Although the programme originally aired as a series of specials beginning in 1983, its only revival during the surveyed period occurred in 2013. *Benefits Street* generated the most significant spike in media attention, particularly in 2014, with extensive coverage from both *The Daily Mail* and *The Guardian*. This likely reflects, in part, its short run time. Aired between 2014 and 2015, *Benefits Street* was a highly controversial documentary series portraying life on welfare and attracted widespread national media attention, especially during its first year.

In the tabloid press on the political right, *The Daily Mail* took a moralising stance in its coverage, often using *Benefits Street* to criticise the welfare system. One article reported that the show had received over 1,700 complaints but defended its portrayal, noting: “critics label it ‘poverty porn’ which paints a false picture of life in modern Britain” (*Daily Mail*, 27 January 2014). Another piece went further, calling what the show revealed “a national disgrace” (*Daily Mail*, 18 January 2014). This framing echoed *The Daily Mail*’s approach to real-life stories about differences in income and wealth between families (e.g., *Rich House*, *Poor House*), portraying such programmes as offering emotional insight into social realities through selected depictions of those involved. Notably, while critical of what these depictions say about society, the articles did not explore the structural causes of poverty. Instead, they framed portrayals of welfare as evidence of moral failings in Britain and a threat to personal responsibility. This tone was also present on *The Jeremy Kyle Show*, a British daytime talk show known for its confrontational style. In news coverage of the host’s personal controversies, the show was described as “a human form of bear-baiting” (*Daily Mail*, 28 September 2015)—a reference to a cruel blood sport, suggesting that the show exploited guests for public entertainment.

Similarly to its position on television programming about differences in income and wealth between families (e.g., *Rich House*, *Poor House*), *The Guardian* remained critical of programmes in this category. Notably, while maintaining a critical stance, its coverage revealed both similarities and differences in focus. Whereas earlier coverage on ‘Income and Wealth Differences Between Families’ emphasised perceived social groups through symbols of wealth, in this case the emphasis was on income—whether through employment or benefits. As one article noted, “*Benefits claimants are seen as a different breed, even though ‘hardworking families’ may also subsist on minimum wages topped up by state benefits*” (*The Guardian*, 22.02.2014). As with the previously discussed category, *The Guardian* questioned the reality and authenticity of these portrayals, though its critique here was somewhat less definitive. These programmes were often scrutinised for whether they presented a true or false depiction of welfare. For example, one article stated, “*Benefits Street is a ‘misrepresentation’ of life on welfare, says MP*” (*The Guardian*, 10.01.2014), with coverage frequently framing the individuals featured in relation to their political utility. *The Guardian* treated *Benefits Street* as a political flashpoint, reporting that it revealed a “‘ghetto’ reality” while critically reflecting on how such portrayals were used to shape public understanding of welfare (*The Guardian*, 23.01.2014). Its coverage of *The Jeremy Kyle Show* was even more direct, describing it as “*sadistic moralising*” that conveyed “a wider social resentment” (*The Guardian*, 15.04.2014).

In contrast to *The Guardian*, also on the political left, which appeared uncertain about whether such programmes reflected reality, political theatre, or public voyeurism, *The Daily Mirror*—despite sharing the tabloid format with *The Daily Mail*—took a unique stance in its class-based critique by acknowledging the programmes as a reflection of social reality. In a 2015 opinion column titled “*Robbing workers to reward the idle,*” the show was presented as an example of welfare exploitation, reinforcing moral divides between taxpayers and claimants (*Daily Mirror*, 11 October 2015). However, it should be noted that in 2014, the relative salience of this type of TV programming was more than double in *The Guardian* compared to *The Daily Mirror*.

In comparison to the other broadsheet surveyed, *The Telegraph* acknowledged the controversy surrounding *Benefits Street* but adopted a more observational tone, asking whether it was “*compelling TV or a circus of misery?*” (*The Telegraph*, 12 May 2015). In addition, it did not share the *Daily Mail*’s interest in this type of TV programming and was more restrained and less overtly moralising.

3.15. Fictional Dramas About an Ineffective Government and Welfare System

This category focuses on fictional portrayals of government inefficiency and welfare policy, often delivered through satire or workplace comedy. In the survey, 34.4% of respondents who reported their TV programming consumption selected this category. It includes *The Job Lot* (2013–2015), a sitcom set in a job centre, and *The Thick of It* (2005–2012), a fast-paced satire exposing political spin.

It also includes *Yes Minister* (1980–1984), an older programme that continues to be invoked in media commentary, as described below.

As will be shown, a common theme across references to these programmes was the perceived absurdity of current government and civil service practices. This perception was potentially reflected in the political alignment of viewers: survey respondents who consumed this type of programming were more likely to support non-mainstream parties on the political left, such as the Liberal Democrats and the Green Party, possibly indicating dissatisfaction with the political mainstream. They also tended to identify as left leaning in political orientation relative to the centre or right.

Graph 4: Relative Salience of 'Fictional Dramas About an Ineffective Government and Welfare System' in British Newspapers (2005–2024)

The graph above shows that coverage across all outlets peaked earliest in *The Guardian* in 2010, followed by a smaller peak between 2012 and 2014 (graph 4), particularly in *The Daily Mail*, *The Guardian*, and *The Telegraph*. In contrast, this category of programming never reached a comparable level of focus in *The Daily Mirror* (graph 4).

The Thick of It gained notable prominence in *The Guardian*, especially around its extended 2009 run and the release of its film adaptation. Yet, there is something notable about *The Guardian*'s attention to this type of TV programming during that period, unmatched by the coverage or concerns of other outlets. It coincided with a shift in the newspaper's political stance—from supporting both the Labour Party and the Liberal Democrats in 2005 to endorsing only the Liberal Democrats in 2010. Coverage ranged from emphasising the programme's popularity and public relevance, suggesting it reflected a broader normative outlook among its readership: "*The Thick of It draws more than a million viewers*" (*The Guardian*, 26 October 2009). It also served as a medium for self-reflection and even self-criticism, with one columnist writing: "*Way back in Late Blair Era, circa 2005, when The Thick of It first surfaced as a hit sitcom, I took against it. At one level the problem was obvious. It was too much like my day job as a Westminster-based political journalist to be enjoyable*" (*The Guardian*, 23 October 2009). Indeed, the programme's function as a vehicle for self-critique appeared to shift after the 2010 general election and the formation of the coalition government between the Conservative and Liberal Democrat parties. A later article remarked: "*The Thick of It satirised the final years of New Labour. But will it find much to laugh at in a coalition that's already unravelling?*" (*The Guardian*, 18 February 2011).

From 2012 onwards, the relative salience of these TV programming types was largely equal in *The Daily Mail*, *The Guardian*, and *The Telegraph* (Graph 4), maintaining a shared focus on using satire

as a vehicle for critiquing perceived government incompetence. However, following the change in government in 2010, this programming no longer carried the same degree of critical self-reflection as it had in the pre-2009 period for the guardian. A 2013 article described the thick of it as “*the sharpest political comedy of our time*” (The Guardian, 2013), and weekly features highlighted standout lines like: “*He’s so dense, light bends around him*” (The Guardian, 2012). Yes Minister was occasionally referenced in op-eds discussing real-life ministerial decisions, though less frequently. The Job Lot appeared mostly in culture roundups, with limited political framing.

In The Daily Mail, Yes Minister served as a touchstone for bureaucratic absurdity. One article noted, “*In the language of Yes Minister, these unchanging targets are a triumph of political illusion over reality*” (Daily Mail, 2013), while another reflected, “*You only have to compare the 1980s classic Yes Minister with its 21st-century equivalents to see how far standards have fallen*” (Daily Mail, 2014). The Thick of It was used to mock real-world political chaos, with coverage describing a party scandal as being managed by “*a Malcolm Tucker-style enforcer*”, a main character in the thick of it (Daily Mail, 2013). The Job Lot, by contrast, received only passing mentions, such as in a listing: “*A send-up of life in a Job Centre with Russell Tovey.*” Similarly of the political right, The Telegraph drew explicit parallels between political missteps and satire, describing one ministerial blunder as “*pure Yes Minister territory*” (The Telegraph, 2013). The Thick of It was mentioned sparingly, usually in entertainment columns or in critiques of media management failures, and The Job Lot was largely absent from Telegraph coverage.

The Daily Mirror gave the least attention overall. It referenced The Job Lot once as “*a sitcom about the quirks of job centre life,*” but offered no deeper engagement. The Thick of It and Yes Minister were rarely, if ever, mentioned, suggesting a lower reliance on satire in its editorial framing of politics.

3.16. Real-life Stories of Individuals Finding Unexpected Wealth

This TV programming type includes shows such as *Cash in the Attic* (2002–2012; revived in 2022) and *Antiques Roadshow* (1979–present), both of which centre on ordinary people discovering unexpected financial value in old belongings. Among respondents who reported their TV programming preferences, 42.7% selected this category, making it the second most frequently chosen overall.

Graph 5: Relative Salience of ‘Real-life Stories of Individuals Finding Unexpected Wealth’ in British Newspapers (2005–2024)

Peaks in the relative salience of these programmes were observed between 2010 and 2011 in *The Guardian*, with a second peak occurring in 2014. As attention to this category declined in *The Guardian*, coverage increased in *The Daily Mail*, building to a peak in 2015 and rising again from 2021 (Graph 5). As will be described below, this genre attracted sustained interest across a range of newspapers and political orientations. However, differences emerged in how the programmes were framed. On the political right, particularly in *The Daily Mail*, this category was presented as an accepted and valued expression of national identity—standing in contrast to its more critical reception in *The Guardian*. This divergence in framing may help explain the survey findings: viewers of this programming type were more likely to lean politically right and were significantly more likely to vote Conservative. Both effects remained statistically significant after applying Bonferroni correction.

In both *The Guardian* and *The Daily Mail*, these shows were linked to a shared cultural orientation—a portrayal of the "middle" of British society. For example, *The Guardian* conveyed this sentiment with a degree of irony: “*Sunday evening on the telly was a miserable one of middle England, middle-class mediocrity. There was something of the Daily Mail about it all. Antiques Roadshow (BBC1, Sunday) came from Ironbridge in Shropshire, or more specifically Blists Hill Victorian Town, where you can pretend you are your great-great-great grandparents*” (*The Guardian*, 15 February 2010). Similarly, the programme was used to symbolise perceived cultural shallowness. As one columnist wrote: “*It’s an Antiques Roadshow attitude to art, with posh experts telling us a bit about ‘quality’ and ‘provenance’, before getting to the juicy punchline of the price tag, and I hate it*” (*The Guardian*, 12 July 2010).

As with *The Guardian*’s coverage of fictional television about government inefficiency and welfare systems during the same period, there is evidence of discomfort with what these programmes suggest about society. The tone often implied an effort to distinguish *Guardian* readers from a more broadly defined British public—particularly those associated with *The Daily Mail*. While affirming that these programmes speak to a common British cultural sensibility, *The Guardian*’s distaste for them was at times used to critique the political establishment, from which the paper was increasingly distancing itself at this point in time. For example, in response to a budget speech, one article stated: “*Most of the people tuning in to the Chancellor of the Exchequer’s speech will have had one question on their minds: ‘What happened to Cash in the Attic?’ Any viewer hoping Alistair Darling might yet oblige them by producing some hidden treasure—an old clock, say, that might fetch enough at auction to finance a gastric band operation—were to be disappointed*” (*The Guardian*, 22 April 2009).

Whereas these shows were used by *The Guardian* as a vehicle for critique—both of political and cultural groups in the UK—their portrayal in the other newspapers surveyed more often affirmed their place as a positive, normative part of British identity. *The Daily Mail* presented these programmes as celebrations of national heritage and everyday life. Its coverage ranged from general TV listings to stories that framed the shows as reflections of shared cultural values. One article, for instance, stated: “*We’re just a very typical local auction house so you, as you can imagine, it was something of a surprise. This is the ultimate Cash in the Attic story*” (*The Daily Mail*, 12 November 2010).

The Telegraph adopted a more subdued tone, often referencing these shows within broader lifestyle columns. For example, one article noted that *Antiques Roadshow* “*still holds its charm as Britain’s gentle Sunday ritual*” (*The Telegraph*, 2012). *The Daily Mirror* offered more human-interest coverage, particularly in relation to *Antiques Roadshow* specials. A 2017 article described one episode as “*the most moving Roadshow yet,*” featuring Holocaust survivors sharing heirlooms with heartbreaking histories (*Daily Mirror*, 14 January 2017). Another reported on a segment where a Chinese bowl used for loose change turned out to be worth £312,000 (*Daily Mirror*, 23 May 2018).

4. Discussion

In the introductory section of this paper, we set out the potential benefits of considering TV programming types as a means to understand political behaviour, particularly in relation to economic

inequality and demands for redistribution. We highlighted how empirical limitations in validating traditional models of political behaviour—such as the median voter hypothesis (Meltzer & Richard, 1981)—have contributed to the development of a range of perceptual models. These models aim to account for the complexity of what is perceived as fair, for whom, and in what context (Cavaillé, 2023; Condon & Wichowsky, 2020). In this context, we proposed that TV programming may play a salient role—both in directing attention to perceived, situated economic contexts, and in shaping responses that extend beyond deliberative or reflexive reasoning. Specifically, TV programming may relate to political perceptions and attitudes through pre-conscious mechanisms, such as ideologically filtered attention (Waldfogel et al., 2021).

What we find—based on survey data—is evidence of possible associations between self-reported consumption of specific TV programme types and both political leanings and party affiliation. This finding is further supported by two additional streams of evidence: the degree of consideration given to these programmes in print and digital media outlets in ways that relate to political leaning, and qualitative analysis of how these programmes were received in those outlets.

A synthesis of results across the varied datasets used suggests that narratives contained in TV programming consumption types has implications not only for political orientation and party affiliation, but also for broader comprehension of economic inequality itself. For example, we find that individuals who reported consuming real-life TV stories about people living in poverty or on welfare were also more likely to place income inequality among the top three societal issues in Britain. Qualitative analysis of these TV programming types shows that, regardless of a newspaper's political orientation, coverage of these issues often employed subtle linguistic features. These features tended to focus on the mechanisms of income generation—whether through benefits and welfare, or through employment. In contrast, those who consumed TV programming that focused on income and wealth differences between families were 16% more likely to rank wealth inequality as one of the top three forms of inequality in Britain and similarly focused in qualitative newspapers on luxury status symbols of wealth. Moreover, consumers of real-life TV stories about people living in poverty or on welfare were also more likely to support the Labour Party over the Conservative Party. This pattern corresponded with left-leaning media outlets such as *The Guardian* and *The Mirror*. In the *Guardian*, there was a critical reception of these depictions of social beneficiaries. Some coverage suggested that the shows did not faithfully represent individuals in receipt of social benefits, but instead the effects of austerity measures. The *Mirror* expressed similar concerns—though to a lesser extent—focusing more on how such portrayals reinforced class distinctions.

The results section of this paper also advances the literature by highlighting the presence of multiple forms of TV programme narratives in media consumption among the British public, which are associated with differences in perceptions of wealth inequality. Rather than a singular, dominant type of TV programming being consumed, we found it was typical for respondents to have consumed multiple types. More than half of these respondents reported watching more than two types, with some consuming as many as nine. Moreover, the breadth of TV programming types consumed varied both in their thematic focus (e.g., heroes in the public vs. private sectors) and in the kinds of social differences they emphasised—whether they highlighted contrasts between social groups (e.g., the rich vs. the poor; social beneficiaries vs. taxpayers) or focused instead on more undifferentiated portrayals of everyday individuals. There was also notable variability in tone and format. Some programmes were more extreme and dramatized—such as fictional portrayals of elite families—while others were grounded in more relatable, everyday experiences, such as shows featuring individuals who unexpectedly discover wealth (e.g., *Antiques Roadshow*).

However, it is questionable, given the range of TV programme types surveyed, whether we can how far we measuring the comprehension of perceptions of economic inequality per se. Rather, it may be more accurate to say we are capturing narratives about income and wealth—narratives that are sometimes framed in terms of inequality but are not necessarily derivative of economic inequality as a verified construct translated to the public through the media, as is typically assumed in studies of media

representations of inequality (e.g., McGovern et al., 2023). While our results clearly suggest that these programmes influence how individuals perceive income and wealth inequality in Britain, the sheer variety of content—ranging from dramatized portrayals of elites to everyday stories of sudden wealth—extends well beyond conventional definitions of economic inequality. We demonstrate that such programming has implications for how inequality is perceived, particularly in relation to concepts such as fairness, deservingness, and political trust, all of which are reflected in qualitative accounts of everyday perceptions of economic inequality in Britain (Pereira et al., 2024).

Our qualitative inspection also revealed important distinctions at the level of representation. What is treated as "true" or legitimate in the portrayal of economic difference varied significantly according to both the mode of communication (e.g., broadsheet vs. tabloid) and the political orientation of the newspaper (left vs. right). These differences may have shaped how TV programmes were received and interpreted by media outlets and their audiences.

We found that stories portraying income and wealth differences between families—especially those involving interactions between the rich and the poor—were received differently depending on both media format and political alignment. In tabloid outlets, such as *The Daily Mail*, depictions of both wealthy and low-income families were often presented as meaningful, valid representations of social reality. These portrayals were treated as reflective of everyday life in Britain. In contrast, broadsheet outlets—especially *The Guardian*—tended to frame these same programmes as sensationalised or lacking in authenticity. In addition, there was a notable discomfort in *The Guardian* with what might be perceived as "looking down" at the lives of the poor, with commentary often questioning whether such depictions exploit their subjects rather than reveal the effects of austerity or broader economic conditions.

This distinction—centring on what constitutes reality and what *should* be considered legitimate cultural representation—was also evident in the contrasting treatment of programmes like *Antiques Roadshow*, which features ordinary individuals discovering unexpected wealth. While *The Daily Mail* frequently celebrated such content as a form of cultural heritage and a reflection of shared aspirations, *The Guardian* at times framed it as classless or representative of 'Middle England' values deemed beneath the assumed cultural sensibilities of its readership.

We should also consider the internal reliability and validity of the survey instrument used. Notably, 16.8% of respondents either chose not to answer or reported not consuming any of the TV programmes listed. We also found partial evidence indicating the presence of latent factors in television programming type consumption; within Component 3 of the factor analysis, consumption patterns appeared to move in opposite directions. Moreover, as reflected in the qualitative historical analysis of news media reporting, time is a complex issue. While some TV programmes continue to hold sustained relevance in the cultural imagination long after they have finished airing, others are perceived as flashpoints with a more restricted timeframe. From this perspective, these programmes should neither be seen as saturating representations of income and wealth narratives in society nor as fixed or enduring types. Indeed, in many ways, this is inevitable: culture is not a fixed object, but a site of ongoing innovation (Marková, 2012). This underscores the need for a continually evolving research agenda—one that remains exploratory and responsive to change. As new forms of media—particularly social media—continue to develop, offering increasingly differentiated content in both format and normative framing, the types and breadth of narratives available will continue to expand. This demands a responsive and adaptive approach. Indeed, an iterative methodology is assumed—one that continually reassesses both the types of programmes under study and how they are received within shifting media and political contexts.

5. Concluding Remarks

To conclude, this paper contributes to the literature by drawing on political science, psychology, and media studies to describe the variety of TV programming types that shape everyday thinking on

issues of income and wealth. These programmes, in part, serve as a basis for how reified forms of knowledge—such as economic inequality—are received and understood. They create a space in which questions of fairness—what is fair, for whom, and in what contexts—are actively considered. This space is understood to operate even at pre-conscious levels, influencing the salience of political ideologies and shaping perceptions of economic inequality. These perceptions may be shaped by segregation within media environments and may even extend to influence what is accepted as true or real.

A key strength of this paper lies in the breadth of its analysis, particularly in relating patterns of media consumption to differences in how income and wealth inequality are perceived. However, there are important methodological limitations. Chief among these is the difficulty of making causal claims in a cross-sectional and exploratory study that lacks historical data. Specifically, we cannot directly assert the processes through which differences in political orientation, party affiliation, perceptions of inequality, and types of TV programming consumption have emerged. Nonetheless, tentative suggestions are offered based on trends and qualitative analysis of how these TV programming types are received in print and digital media.

At the same time, we should be cautious not to reduce research recommendations to simply refining measurement tools—for example, by adding more questions on TV programming types to establish causality. While such methodological improvements may be valuable, they should not come at the expense of the broader, exploratory aim. Media programming is continually changing, likely in response to the evolving and fragmenting media environment that promotes alternative narratives, particularly across different platforms such as social media. As culture is a continually evolving and dynamic phenomenon, research in this area must remain flexible and responsive. With new forms of communication—especially digital and social media—constantly emerging, the study of media, inequality, and perception benefits from a dynamic and adaptive research programme.

6. Appendix:

Appendix A: Top-Three Perceived Forms of Inequality in Britain (Percentage of Participants Reporting "Yes")

Type of Inequality	Perceived Inequality (Yes %)	No (%)
Working conditions	11.7	83.6
Income	34.4	61
Race and ethnicity	21.1	74.3
Education	15.9	79.4
Economic differences between countries	6.8	88.6
Sexual orientation (LGBTQ+)	7.4	87.9
Urban/Rural	6.6	88.7
Transport and infrastructure	5.8	89.5
Wealth	32.3	63
Gender	10	85.3
Migration and citizenship	16.5	78.8
Health, illness and disability	30.9	64.4
Age	13.5	81.8
Housing	27.5	67.8

Justice before the law	8.9	86.4
Environment and climate change	4.5	90.8
Other type of inequality	0.9	94.4
Do not perceive any inequality	4.1	91.3

Appendix B: Pearson Correlations Among TV Programming types.

TV Programming Types	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
1. Real-life Stories of Everyday Individuals Achieving Success	–								
2. Real-life Stories of Everyday Individuals Finding Unexpected Wealth	0.16	–							
3. Real-life Stories of Everyday Individuals Living in Poverty and/or on Welfare Payments	0.18	0.11	–						
4. Real-life Stories About the Differences in Income and Wealth Between Families	0.19	0.15	0.37	–					
5. Real-life Stories of the Everyday Heroes in the Private Sector	0.23	0.18	0.28	0.33	–				
6. Real-life Stories of the Everyday Heroes Workers in the Public Sector	0.2	0.12	0.26	0.24	0.22	–			
7. Fictional Dramas About an Ineffective Government and Welfare System	–0.01	0.08	0.03	–0.02	0.07	0.02	–		
8. Fictional Dramas About the Elite and Their Families	0.08	–0.02	0.08	0.08	0.07	0.11	0.18	–	
9. Real-life Stories of the Everyday Lives of Rich Individuals	0.12	0.02	0.24	0.22	0.16	0.13	–0.02	0.18	–

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